

Agentic AI for 15-Minute Single Day-Ahead Coupling Market Analytics in Central and Eastern Europe

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Abstract: The shift to 15-minute Market Time Units (MTU) in the Single Day-Ahead Coupling (SDAC) increases temporal granularity but complicates the interpretation of intra-hour electricity price spikes and rapid ramps. This paper examines whether architectural decomposition improves the reliability of Large Language Model (LLM)-based diagnostics in price-only settings. We compare a proposed agentic workflow, featuring structured context extraction, spike/ramp detection, hypothesis generation, consistency checks and explicit uncertainty calibration, against a monolithic LLM baseline. The paper contributes: (i) a reproducible benchmark for 15-minute diagnostic question answering in day-ahead markets, (ii) an agentic architecture tailored to structured time-series reasoning with explicit uncertainty handling, (iii) empirical evidence that decomposition and verification improve evidence grounding and trustworthiness in market analytics. The evaluation includes 150 benchmark cases from six Central and Eastern European bidding zones (Bulgaria, Czechia, Hungary, Poland, Romania, Slovakia), comprising 47 spike and 103 ramp cases. Using identical inputs, we assess automatic reliability metrics and human ratings. The agentic workflow improves reliability ($\Delta = +0.164$, 95% CI [+0.132, +0.195]) and significantly increases calibrated price-only disclaimers ($\Delta = +0.560$), while reducing unsupported exogenous assertions ($\Delta = -0.387$). Human evaluation confirms higher overall quality (+0.74), helpfulness (+1.06), and correctness (+0.94), with a 65.5% pairwise win rate. Results demonstrate that structured decomposition and verification enhance grounding, calibration and trustworthiness in high-frequency electricity market diagnostics.

Keywords: agentic workflows, tool-augmented LLMs, SDAC, 15-minute MTU, day-ahead electricity market analytics

1. Introduction

The adoption of 15-minute Market Time Units (MTU) in the Single Day-Ahead Coupling (SDAC) structurally changes the European electricity market by increasing the temporal granularity [1]. While this transition aims to provide more insights about intra-hour system conditions, it also raises certain challenges for market participants, analysts and system operators such as fast ramps in residual load or more sensitive prices to short-lived imbalances, making it more difficult to explain why a specific quarter-hour exhibits a spike or a rapid price change [2]. However, it is important for economic agents to understand the reasons that cause these changes because they can impact the bidding strategies, risk management and post-trade analysis, especially in interconnected regions where cross-border effects propagate quickly [3].

Due to their ability to generate coherent explanations, summarize heterogeneous inputs and support interactive Question Answering (QA), Large Language Models (LLMs) have emerged as a useful tool for analytics and decision support [4]. Despite their progress, LLMs' use for electricity market diagnostics remains problematic. First, quarter-hour market analysis is strongly numerical and time-indexed: explanations must align with timestamps, computed deltas and short windows of contextual evidence [5]. Second, LLMs can produce plausible but weakly grounded causal narratives and can be unstable across repeated runs, limitations that directly affect trustworthiness when users need reliable reasoning [6].

This paper proposes an agentic workflow for SDAC day-ahead analytics that aims to address these limitations. Specifically, we target the task of explaining why a given 15-minute SDAC day-ahead price interval exhibits an unusual level or change (e.g., an intra-hour spike or rapid ramp), using only a bounded local window of the published day-ahead price series. We focus on price-only inputs to isolate the effect of architectural decomposition and verification, without confounding gains with access to exogenous variables, and to explicitly test calibrated uncertainty under limited observability. The main idea is that planned, targeted extraction of time-window evidence, consistency checks and explicit uncertainty handling can yield more reliable diagnostic answers than a single-pass LLM response. Our research question is whether architectural decomposition and verification improve evidence grounding (timestamps and numeric deltas), interval focus and calibration of uncertainty in price-only settings. To

isolate the effect of the architecture, we compare the agentic system against a LLM that receives the same case inputs and questions but lacks explicit decomposition and verification.

Our evaluation relies on a benchmark of cases constructed from public market data, with emphasis on situations where 15-minute resolution materially changes the interpretation (intra-hour spikes and rapid ramping patterns). We construct cases from publicly available SDAC day-ahead prices published via the ENTSO-E Transparency Platform API, focusing on six Central and Eastern Europe (CEE) bidding zones (Bulgaria, Czechia, Hungary, Poland, Romania and Slovakia) over 2025-10-01 to 2025-10-13. Each case defines a zone and a target quarter-hour, provides a bounded time window of price series and asks for a diagnosis with evidence anchored in timestamps and numeric values. Concretely, the input contains the target timestamp, a fixed local context window at 15-minute granularity with prices in EUR/MWh and derived indicators used to select and characterize cases (e.g., quarter-hour price deltas and spike/ramp flags).

Therefore, our study brings three contributions to the literature:

- (a) First, we define a reproducible evaluation setup for 15-minute day-ahead diagnostic QA, including a *structured case format* and a protocol for paired comparisons between a LLM baseline and an agentic workflow.
- (b) Second, we propose an agentic design tailored to market analytics over structured time series, emphasizing mechanism-aware reasoning and evidence extraction.
- (c) Third, we provide a comparison focused on European Union member states, highlighting how agentic workflows affect reliability and evidence quality in a region where price dynamics can be sensitive to cross-border interactions.

The motivation for this study arises from the structural transformation of European electricity markets following the adoption of 15-minute MTU in the SDAC. While increased temporal granularity improves market efficiency and better reflects intra-hour system conditions, it also makes price dynamics more volatile and harder to interpret. Intra-hour spikes and rapid ramps can emerge within narrow time windows and small imbalances may translate into sharp price movements. For traders, analysts and system operators, understanding why a specific quarter-hour exhibits an unusual level or change has therefore become both more important and more challenging. At the same time, LLMs are increasingly used for analytical support because of their ability to summarize data and generate explanations. However, in high-frequency, price-only environments, LLMs often produce plausible but weakly grounded causal narratives, sometimes attributing price changes to exogenous drivers without evidence. This creates a trust and reliability gap, particularly in regulated and high-stakes markets.

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows. Section 2 reviews the relevant literature on 15-minute market design in the SDAC, diagnostic analytics in electricity markets, and the use of LLMs for structured reasoning and decision support, with particular emphasis on reliability and uncertainty calibration. Section 3 introduces the proposed agentic architecture, detailing the decomposition into local context extraction, spike/ramp identification, hypothesis generation, consistency verification and explicit uncertainty handling. This section also formalizes the research question and explains the controlled comparison with a monolithic LLM baseline. Section 4 describes the data construction and evaluation framework. It presents the benchmark of 150 price-only cases across six Central and Eastern European bidding zones, explains the case format and metrics, and reports results from automatic reliability indicators, zone-level heterogeneity analysis and human evaluation. Section 5 provides a discussion on practical implications and utility of the findings. Finally, Section 5 concludes by summarizing the main findings, outlining practical implications for market participants and system operators, and suggesting directions for future research on trustworthy AI in high-frequency electricity markets.

2. Literature review

The exponential development of LLMs has accelerated interest toward their integration as a decision support tool across technical domains, including finance, operations and energy systems [7]. While they have a great ability to generate natural-language explanations and support interactive analysis, research also highlights their limitations such as hallucinations, weak calibration of uncertainty and inconsistent citation or evidence usage, particularly in settings requiring precise numerical grounding [8]. In electricity-market analytics, where explanations often depend on time-indexed signals

and short-lived system states, these limitations can significantly reduce trust [9]. This section reviews relevant literature on LLMs for market analytics, agentic workflows and evaluation methodologies.

2.1 LLMs for energy and electricity markets

LLMs play the role of natural-language interfaces for energy data exploration, forecasting assistance and operational decision support [10]. Prior studies highlight LLMs’ ability to interpret complex dashboards, summarize multi-source signals and generate narratives around market events [11]. However, in wholesale electricity markets, structured numerical inputs (prices, volumes, load) represent an important component of analysis [12]. Moreover, it is essential to carefully align the analysis to market timelines and product granularity [13]. As a result, the ability to generate plausible text does not guarantee that it can also provide meaningful and grounded analysis [14].

2.2 Agentic workflows and tool-augmented LLM systems

Agentic workflows or tool-augmented pipelines represent a solution for improving reliability by not answering in a single step but instead planning, calling tools, validating intermediate results and synthesizing a final response [15]. Multi-step architectures have shown improvements in task completion and factual consistency in domains where decomposition and verification matter [16]. In such methodologies, the main benefit is represented by the separation of responsibilities and the forcing of the generation of structured intermediate outputs [17]. Nevertheless, agentic systems also introduce new failure modes: orchestration errors, compounding tool mistakes and overly rigid pipelines that may miss salient signals if the planning step is poor [18].

2.3 Numerical grounding and time series reasoning in LLM outputs

Numerical evidence and time series context represent an important component of electricity market explanations. Literature shows that precise numerical reasoning, especially when the task requires tracking multiple timestamps, computing differences or maintaining consistency across related statements represent a weakness of LLMs [19]. These limitations can be mitigated by using tools that offload arithmetic and enforce explicit references to data points [20]. For evaluation, researchers increasingly operationalize grounding via measurable indicators such as numeric consistency, timestamp coverage and the ability to cite evidence aligned with the question scope [21].

2.4 Market-design context-SDAC and the shift to 15-minute products

In the EU, the price signals and events diagnosis were changed by the transition from hourly to 15-minute products. Patterns that were previously smoothed within an hour become visible as short spikes, step changes or rapid ramps across adjacent quarters [22]. Short-lived constraints, ramping capability limits, forecast errors and changes in residual demand can drive intra-hour variability in high-frequency electricity market [23]. In interconnected markets, these effects propagate across borders [24]. Despite these domain characteristics, the intersection between 15-minute market design and LLM-driven explanatory analytics remains underexplored, particularly for EU-coupled day-ahead contexts.

2.5 Evaluating reliability-evidence focus, stability and unsupported claims

Quality of analytics systems can be determined on several coordinates: correctness, usefulness, evidence support and robustness to paraphrases or repeated runs, which makes the evaluation of LLM-based systems a challenging task [25]. One approach is represented by automated evaluation that approximates these dimensions through proxy metrics, but this method can be sensitive to prompt choices and may not fully capture domain correctness [26]. In this way, a more efficient strategy is to combine (i) automatic metrics with (ii) human assessment on a subset of cases using a structured rubric [27]. This motivates our evaluation design, that is to compute comparable automatic metrics for baseline versus agentic outputs and complement them with manual scoring for plausibility and evidence quality. A structured comparative analysis synthesizing the referenced works is provided in Table 1.

Table 1. Comparison of the previous works

Ref	Objective	Methods	Brief findings	Generative models
[7]	Integrate AI with optimization (AI4OPT) to enhance optimization processes	Survey of AI-enhanced parameter generation, model formulation, and solution methods	AI significantly improves efficiency and effectiveness across optimization stages	AI models broadly (not specific to LLMs)
[8]	Automate nuclear simulations (FLUKA workflow)	Domain-embedded agents, RAG, integration	LLM GUI Reduced error resolution time from days to <1 minute; high accuracy (<0.001% uncertainty)	LLM agents + RAG

[9]	Develop trust scoring for electricity price forecasting (EPF)	Explainable AI (local/global explanations, SHAP-based trust score)	>85% accuracy in identifying good/bad predictions under distribution shift	ML models + XAI (no generative model)
[10]	Review LLM applications in energy systems	Literature review of 22 LLM types and enhancement techniques	Identifies 13 LLM roles; highlights opportunities and challenges	GPT, LLaMA, ChatGLM, etc.
[11]	Review LLM applications in power systems	Analysis of 30 real-world applications	LLMs enhance grid ops, markets, security; reliability challenges	LLMs
[12]	Forecast electricity prices using market structure (X-Model)	Supply-demand curve modeling, lasso estimation, simulation	Captures nonlinear price behavior; improves spike prediction	No generative model
[13]	Redesign trading products for renewable integration	Market design and economic analysis	Finer granularity and power-profile trade improve flexibility	No generative model
[14]	Mitigate hallucinations in LLMs using knowledge graphs	KG integration with LLMs; evaluation benchmarks	KGs enhance reliability but open challenges remain	LLM + Knowledge Graph
[15]	Standardize LLM agents in building energy sector	JSON-based agent schema + open-source library	Enables reproducible and shareable LLM agents	LLM agents
[16]	Improve Text-to-SQL for power dispatching	Agent-based LLM framework with intent recognition + SQL validation	Significant gains in execution accuracy; robust across LLMs	LLM agents
[17]	Automate building energy modeling (BEM)	Multi-agent LLM planning workflow	Outperforms naive prompting and manual modeling in accuracy and efficiency	LLM agent workflow
[18]	Differentiate AI Agents vs Agentic AI	Conceptual taxonomy and comparative framework	Agentic AI enables dynamic decomposition, autonomy, collaboration	LLM-based agentic systems
[19]	Explore LLM capabilities in power sector	Commentary on LLM integration strategies	Calls for RAG, fine-tuning, and domain embedding	LLMs (general)
[20]	Improve smart building O&M querying	Fine-tuned LLM + RAG + Knowledge Graph	95.5% execution accuracy; outperforms GPT-4, Llama-70B	Fine-tuned LLM + RAG
[21]	Survey RAG evaluation methods	Comprehensive review of RAG benchmarks and frameworks	Identifies evaluation gaps in hybrid retrieval-generation systems	LLM + RAG
[22]	Assess impact of 15-min contracts in EPEX	Bayesian structural time series	Up to 28% price reduction; better renewable integration	No generative model
[23]	Model intraday vs day-ahead price difference	Normalizing flow (deep generative density model) + XAI	Highest accuracy and narrowest prediction intervals	Deep generative model (normalizing flow)
[24]	Analyze cross-border electricity market interdependencies	Econometric + Nash-Cournot models	Strong seasonal cross-border price dependencies	No generative model
[25]	Automate renewable siting ordinance extraction	LLM + decision tree framework	85–90% accuracy; supports large-scale policy modeling	LLM
[26]	Auto-building energy modeling via prompt engineering	Prompt engineering (few-shot, CoT strategies)	Effective ABEM without fine-tuning; compact LLMs viable	LLM (prompt-based)
[27]	Optimize data selection for human evaluation	Metric variance selectors, IRT-based selection	~70% data sufficient for equivalent evaluation reliability	No generative model
[28]	Review LLM applications in building energy	Literature review + survey	LLMs enhance control, automation, compliance; challenges remain	LLMs
[29]	Review Transformers & LLMs in energy; propose Agentic Digital Twin	Review + conceptual framework	Introduces Agentic Digital Twin integrating FMs	LLMs, Foundation Models
[30]	Forecast German quarter-hour spot markets	Elastic net regression + economic strategy evaluation	Forecasting yields substantial trading benefits	No generative model

Prior work suggests that LLMs can be used as an analytics tool, but they also present some limitations [28]. Agentic workflows and tool-use promise improvements, yet there is limited evidence

isolating the effect of agentic decomposition for EU day-ahead market diagnostics at 15-minute resolution [29]. Moreover, 15-minute products increase the need for interval-specific reasoning [30]. Our study addresses these gaps by (i) defining a structured benchmark of 15-minute SDAC-related diagnostic cases constructed from public market data, (ii) implementing an agentic workflow that emphasizes planning, evidence extraction, verification and explicit uncertainty handling, and (iii) comparing it against an LLM baseline under identical inputs to quantify reliability improvements attributable to the architecture.

3. Methodology

This study aims to determine if an agentic LLM workflow achieves a stronger performance than a single LLM baseline in terms of day-ahead market analytics at 15-minute resolution. Our main hypothesis is that splitting workflow in multiple steps (planning, structured extraction, verification, synthesis) produces outputs that are (i) more consistently grounded in the provided time series, (ii) more focused on the target 15-minute interval and (iii) less prone to unsupported claims than a monolithic prompt-response baseline.

Let $z \in \mathcal{Z}$ denote a bidding zone (CEE focus) and let the day-ahead price be observed on a 15-minute grid:

$$\mathcal{T} = \{t_1, t_2, \dots, t_n\}, \Delta t = 15 \text{ minutes} \quad (1)$$

with prices $p_z \in \mathbb{R}$ in EUR/MWh. Each query analyses a target timestamp $t^* \in \mathcal{T}$ and a local context window.

3.1 Case construction using ENTSO-E day-ahead prices

We queried the ENTSO-E Transparency Platform API [31] in order to obtain the public day-ahead price series $\{(t, p_z(t))\}_{t \in \mathcal{T}_{z,d}}$ for each zone z and day d . A case c is defined by a tuple:

$$c = (z, d, t^*, p_c, q_c) \quad (2)$$

where t^* is an event timestamp and q_c represents a natural-language question template and:

$$p_c = \{(t, p_z(t)) \mid t \in [t^* - H_{pre}, t^* - H_{post}]\} \quad (3)$$

is the local price window around t^* with fixed H_{pre}, H_{post} (2 hours each). To avoid near-duplicate cases, we apply a minimum separation constraint. If two candidates t_i^*, t_j^* satisfy:

$$|t_i^* - t_j^*| < \tau_{min}, \tau_{min} = 60 \text{ minutes} \quad (4)$$

we retain at most one.

Our cases suite contains only instances where the 15-minute granularity matters. For each zone-day series, define the daily empirical quantile function $Q_{z,d}(\alpha)$ of $\{p_z(t)\}$. A timestamp t is a spike candidate if:

$$p_z(t) \geq Q_{z,d}(0.95) \quad (5)$$

Define the discrete 15-minute price change:

$$\Delta p_z(t) = p_z(t) - p_z(t - \Delta t) \quad (6)$$

and its absolute magnitude $|\Delta p_z(t)|$. A timestamp t is a ramp candidate if:

$$|\Delta p_z(t)| \geq Q_{z,d}^\Delta(0.90) \quad (7)$$

where $Q_{z,d}^\Delta(\alpha)$ is the daily empirical quantile of $\{|\Delta p_z(t)|\}$ over valid t .

For each case, we define a label $y_c \in \{spike, ramp\}$ based on the detector that produced it.

3.2 Systems under comparison

Let \mathcal{J}_c denote the structured input for case c , consisting of (z, q_c, p_c) encoded in JSON-like form.

3.2.1 Baseline monolithic LLM

The baseline variant for our study is represented by a single LLM call:

$$a_c^{(B)} = f_\theta(\mathcal{J}_c) \quad (8)$$

where f_θ is the chosen Gemini model (*gemini-2.5-flash-lite*) with fixed configuration (temperature = 0).

3.2.2 Agentic workflow mapping

Figure 1 summarizes the proposed agentic workflow, showing the sequence of specialized agents used to plan, structure the data, perform quantitative analysis, reason about mechanisms, verify claims and synthesize the final response.

Figure 1. Agentic workflow overview

The agentic workflow splits the process into multiple steps:

$$a_c^{(A)} = S(V(K(Q(M(P(\mathcal{J}_c)))))) \quad (9)$$

where $a_c^{(A)}$ is the final structured answer for case c and each operator corresponds to a role-specific agent:

- *Planner Agent (P)* represents the first layer of our architecture. Its role is to interpret the query and produce a task plan that specifies what evidence is required and which intermediate computations should be performed. Concretely, P understands the user's intent (e.g., spike explanation versus ramping explanation), identifies the target interval $I_c = [t^*, t^* + \Delta t]$ and defines constraints.
- *Market Data Agent (M)* standardizes data ordering, computes derived columns and provides a structured representation used by later stages to ground the explanation by transforming the raw local price p_c into a deterministic feature table $x_c(t)$, including the discrete quarter-hour change $\Delta p_z(t) = p_z(t) - p_z(t - \Delta t)$.
- *Quantitative Analysis Agent (Q)* aims to make the results less dependent on the LLM's free-form arithmetic. Thus, Q performs lightweight quantitative checks by identifying the largest $|\Delta p|$ within a target neighbourhood, ranking candidate intervals by magnitude and generating summary statistics.
- *Mechanism Agent (K)* assesses the credibility of the current draft diagnosis and detected patterns under the market mechanism context and the resolution of analysis (15-minute MTU) and outputs plausibility checks, candidate mechanisms and warnings based only on the provided inputs. In particular, K enforces constraints such as (i) avoiding causal statements that require missing exogenous signals and (ii) ensuring that the narrative remains anchored to the specified target interval rather than drifting to unrelated periods.
- *Verifier Agent (V)* forces justifications for statements. In this way, the agent performs a verification over intermediate claims and planned conclusions, explicitly flagging (i) unsupported assertions, (ii) missing inputs that would be required to justify a stronger claim and (iii) inconsistencies between stated drivers and the computed feature table.
- *Synthesizer Agent (S)* generates the final answer in a strict JSON schema. The synthesis is constrained to preserve the constructed evidence lines (timestamps and numeric deltas). The narrative components (drivers, uncertainty, summary) are phrased to reflect the available information.

3.2.3 Agentic workflow without the Market Data agent

To isolate the marginal contribution of structured market-data extraction, we define an ablation variant that removes the Market Data Agent from the workflow. In this variant, the pipeline remains unchanged except that the Market Data step is skipped. Downstream agents operate on the remaining inputs under the same strict JSON schema and synthesis constraints. All other factors (case inputs, model configuration, and evaluation protocol) are held constant to preserve a controlled comparison.

3.3 Automated evaluation

Given the fact that exogenous causal attribution cannot be validated from price-only inputs, the automated metrics used in our study aim to quantify grounding and focus properties. Let ε_c be the set of evidence lines produced for case c and let $|\varepsilon_c|$ be its cardinality.

3.3.1 Timestamp coverage

Let $1_{ts}(e) = 1$ if evidence line e contains an ISO timestamp, else 0. Then:

$$TSCov(c) = \frac{1}{|\varepsilon_c|} \sum_{e \in \varepsilon_c} 1_{ts}(e) \quad (10)$$

with $TSCov(c) = 0$ if $|\varepsilon_c| = 0$.

3.3.2 Delta-format coverage

Let $1_{\Delta}(e) = 1$ if e contains a standardized delta format, else 0:

$$DeltaCov(c) = \frac{1}{|\varepsilon_c|} \sum_{e \in \varepsilon_c} 1_{\Delta}(e) \quad (11)$$

3.3.3 Target-neighbourhood focus

We define an indicator that at least one evidence timestamp lies in the neighbourhood $\mathcal{N}_c(\delta)$:

$$NearTarget(c) = 1 \ (\exists t \in \mathcal{T}(\varepsilon_c) \text{ s.t. } |t - t^*| \leq \delta) \quad (12)$$

where $\mathcal{T}(\varepsilon_c)$ extracts timestamps present in evidence lines.

3.3.4 Calibration

Based on the fact that each case provides only a day-ahead price series, a well-calibrated answer's true causal drivers cannot be confirmed from prices alone. We operationalize this as a simple binary indicator that checks whether the output contains a price-only limitation disclaimer. Let the model output for case c include *uncertainty* field composed by a list of strings and *final_summary* field represented by a string. We define the pool of text where a disclaimer may appear as:

$$T(c) = (\cup_{u \in uncertainty_c} \{u\}) \cup \{final_summary_c\} \quad (13)$$

We then define a set of disclaimer patterns \mathcal{P} that indicate price-only limitations. Next, we define the calibration indicator:

$$Cal(c) = 1(\exists x \in T(c) \text{ s.t. } \exists p \in \mathcal{P} : p \subset x) \quad (14)$$

where $p \subset x$ denotes that pattern p appears in the text x . Thus, $Cal(c) \in \{0,1\}$ equals 1 if the output explicitly states that causal attribution is limited by price-only inputs and 0 otherwise.

3.3.5 Unsupported exogenous assertions

Although the model may mention exogenous concepts as missing information, we penalize only asserted exogenous drivers stated without hedging. Let $UEA(c)$ be the count of exogenous keywords appearing in non-hedged sentences within *top_drivers* and *final_summary* fields:

$$UEA(c) = \sum_{s \in S_c} \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} 1(k \in s) \cdot 1(Hedge(s)) \quad (15)$$

where S_c is the set of claim-bearing sentences, \mathcal{K} is the exogenous keyword set and $Hedge(s)$ detects uncertainty markers.

3.3.6 Reliability score

We combine the above into a reliability-oriented composite metric:

$$Rel(c) = \omega_1 TSCov(c) + \omega_2 DeltaCov(c) + \omega_3 NearTarget(c) + \omega_4 Disc(c) - \omega_5 g(UEA(c)) \quad (16)$$

where $g(\cdot)$ is a saturating penalty and weights ω_i are fixed a priori. The key comparison is the paired difference:

$$\Delta Rel(c) = Rel^{(A)}(c) - Rel^{(B)}(c) \quad (17)$$

3.4 Human evaluation

To consolidate our conclusions, we added a human evaluation. For each case c annotators rate baseline and agentic outputs as it follows:

$$r_{c,j}^{(m)}(s) \in \{1,2,3,4,5\}, \quad s \in \{A,B\}, m \in \{1, \dots, M\} \quad (18)$$

We define the per-system mean rating:

$$\bar{r}_{c,j}(s) = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{m=1}^M r_{c,j}^{(m)}(s) \quad (19)$$

and compute paired deltas:

$$\Delta r_{c,j} = \bar{r}_{c,j}(A) - \bar{r}_{c,j}(B) \quad (20)$$

3.4 Statistical analysis

For each metric $m(c)$, we compute paired differences $\Delta m(c)$ across all cases and report mean difference:

$$\hat{\mu}_\Delta = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{c=1}^N \Delta m(c) \quad (21)$$

and bootstrap confidence intervals (CIs):

$$CI_{1-\alpha}(\hat{\mu}_\Delta) = [q_{\alpha/2}, q_{1-\alpha/2}] \quad (22)$$

where q are bootstrap quantiles over resampled cases. All analyses are performed both overall and by zone to verify generalization across CEE markets.

3.5 Results validation

To validate our statistical results, we summarize all metrics using paired case-level differences and report nonparametric uncertainty estimates together with standardized effect sizes. For each case c and metric m , we compute the paired difference as:

$$\Delta m_c = m_c^{(agentic)} - m_c^{(baseline)} \quad (23)$$

Then, we report the baseline and agentic sample means:

$$\bar{m}^{(baseline)} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{c=1}^N m_c^{(baseline)} \quad (24)$$

$$\bar{m}^{(agentic)} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{c=1}^N m_c^{(agentic)} \quad (25)$$

and the mean paired effect:

$$\overline{\Delta m} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{c=1}^N \Delta m_c \quad (26)$$

Uncertainty in $\overline{\Delta m}$ is estimated via a case-resampling bootstrap with 5000 resamples. Each bootstrap replicate draws cases with replacement and recomputes $\overline{\Delta m}$. The 95% confidence interval is obtained from the 2.5th and 97.5th percentiles of the bootstrap distribution. To provide a standardized measure of effect magnitude that is comparable across metrics, we report paired Cohen's d , defined as:

$$d = \frac{\overline{\Delta m}}{s_{\Delta m}} \quad (27)$$

$$s_{\Delta m} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N-1} \sum_{c=1}^N (\Delta m_c - \overline{\Delta m})^2} \quad (28)$$

The methodological flowchart is presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Methodological flowchart

4. Results

4.1 Case set and evaluation coverage

Our study aimed to compare the performance of the agentic workflow against the monolithic LLM baseline across 150 price-only cases from Central and Eastern Europe, spanning six bidding zones: Bulgaria, Czechia, Hungary, Poland, Romania and Slovakia. Table 2 reports the distribution across zones.

Table 2. Case composition by zone and case type

Zone	Total cases	Spike cases	Ramp cases	Target time range (UTC)
Bulgaria	22	9	13	2025-10-06 to 2025-10-13
Czechia	27	9	18	2025-10-02 to 2025-10-09
Hungary	24	6	18	2025-10-04 to 2025-10-11
Poland	19	6	13	2025-10-01 to 2025-10-08
Romania	29	8	21	2025-10-05 to 2025-10-12
Slovakia	29	9	20	2025-10-03 to 2025-10-10
All	150	47	103	2025-10-01 to 2025-10-13

4.2 Performance on automatic reliability metrics

The agentic workflow generated more reliable answers than the baseline. Concretely, the agentic workflow brought an improvement of $\Delta = +0.1637$ on average and a 95% CI of $[+0.1323, +0.1945]$, indicating a substantial advantage over the standard LLM. This improvement was mainly generated by the better calibration for price-only inputs. The number of explicit price-only disclaimers was substantially higher in the case of the agentic workflow with $\Delta = +0.56$ and CI of $[+0.4798, +0.64]$. These results align with the intended behaviour of the agentic architecture, that is encouraged to describe observed price dynamics while marking causal drivers as uncertain when no exogenous signals are available. Table 3 summarizes the differences between the agentic workflow and the baseline LLM across the full evaluation set, reporting the mean delta (agentic versus baseline) and 95% bootstrap confidence intervals.

Table 3. Overall metric deltas with 95% bootstrap confidence intervals

Metric	Mean Δ	95% CI	Interpretation
Reliability score	+0.164	[+0.132, +0.195]	Higher is better
Price-only disclaimer presence (Calibration)	+0.560	[+0.480, +0.640]	Higher is better
Unsupported exogenous assertions	-0.387	[-0.687, -0.107]	Lower is better
Exogenous mentions	+13.780	[+13.327, +14.213]	Count difference (higher = more mentions)
Target-neighbourhood focus	+0.000	[0.000, 0.000]	No difference

Figure 3 summarizes the distribution of per-case reliability scores for the baseline and agentic systems (Figure 3a) and visualizes the paired per-case deltas (Figure 3b), highlighting both overall performance and case-level heterogeneity.

(a)

(b)

Figure 3. (a) Distribution of per-case reliability scores (baseline versus agentic), (b) Paired per-case reliability differences (agentic - baseline)

4.3 Unsupported causal claim vs “hypothesis-style” mentions

An important element in price-only settings is to avoid unsupported exogenous attribution (e.g., load as factual drivers without evidence). Our results demonstrate that the proposed agentic workflow reduced unsupported exogenous assertions by $\Delta = -0.3867$ on average. By contrast, the agentic workflow increased exogenous mentions anywhere in the response by $\Delta = +13.78$ (CI [+13.3267, +14.2133]). In this way, the proposed architecture generated more reliable responses by shifting from unhedged causal claims toward explicitly hedged hypothesis. Figure 4 visualizes the trade-off between how often a system mentions exogenous concepts and how often it states them as unsupported assertions, showing baseline and agentic outputs as paired points per case.

Figure 4. Unsupported exogenous assertions versus exogenous mentions

4.4 Target-neighbourhood grounding-ceiling effect

Our results present an overall score of $\Delta = 0.0$ for the target-neighbourhood focus metric. This suggests a ceiling effect. Both systems reliably referenced timestamps near the target interval under the current prompting and/or post-processing constraints. Figure 5 quantifies how tightly each system’s

evidence stays anchored to the target 15-minute episode by plotting the distribution of absolute time distances (in minutes) between timestamps mentioned in evidence and the case’s target timestamp.

Figure 5. Evidence timestamp proximity to the target interval (baseline versus agentic)

4.5 Heterogeneity across bidding zones

Improvements in reliability were observed consistently across zones, with mean Δ reliability score ranging from +0.1289 for Bulgaria to +0.2008 for Slovakia. Notably, Romania and Slovakia gained the strongest results (+0.1825 and +0.2008), while Bulgaria and Czechia show smaller but still positive improvements (+0.1289 and +0.1368). For unsupported exogenous assertions, reductions are strong in several zones such as Hungary and Romania, while in Poland the mean difference is slightly positive and the interval is wide, indicating uncertainty and potential sensitivity to case mix. Table 4 reports per-zone paired deltas (agentic – baseline) for the primary metrics, together with 95% bootstrap confidence intervals, highlighting cross-zone heterogeneity in the observed effects.

Table 4. Per-zone performance deltas (agentic – baseline) with 95% bootstrap confidence intervals

Zone	N	Δ Reliability	Δ Calibration	Δ Unsupported exog assertions	Δ Exog mentions	Δ Target-neighbourhood
Bulgaria	22	+0.129 [+0.048, +0.213]	+0.409 [+0.227, +0.636]	-0.455 [-1.228, +0.227]	+13.682 [+12.591, +14.727]	+0.000 [+0.000, +0.000]
Czechia	27	+0.137 [+0.058, +0.213]	+0.519 [+0.333, +0.704]	-0.037 [-0.556, +0.444]	+14.296 [+13.630, +14.926]	+0.000 [+0.000, +0.000]
Hungary	24	+0.153 [+0.064, +0.245]	+0.500 [+0.292, +0.708]	-0.833 [-1.875, +0.083]	+13.292 [+11.917, +14.542]	+0.000 [+0.000, +0.000]
Poland	19	+0.171 [+0.107, +0.229]	+0.684 [+0.474, +0.895]	+0.105 [-0.737, +0.737]	+14.158 [+12.789, +15.421]	+0.000 [+0.000, +0.000]
Romania	29	+0.183 [+0.123, +0.241]	+0.552 [+0.379, +0.724]	-0.655 [-1.345, +0.000]	+13.586 [+12.517, +14.655]	+0.000 [+0.000, +0.000]
Slovakia	29	+0.201 [+0.128, +0.272]	+0.690 [+0.517, +0.862]	-0.345 [-1.000, +0.276]	+13.724 [+12.621, +14.759]	+0.000 [+0.000, +0.000]
All	150	+0.164 [+0.132, +0.195]	+0.560 [+0.480, +0.640]	-0.387 [-0.687, -0.107]	+13.780 [+13.327, +14.213]	+0.000 [+0.000, +0.000]

Figure 6 shows cross-zone heterogeneity by plotting the mean per-zone improvement in reliability (agentic – baseline) together with 95% bootstrap confidence intervals.

Figure 6. Forest plot of per-zone Δ reliability score with 95% bootstrap confidence intervals

4.6 Ablation study: removing the Market Data agent

Table 5 presents the performance of the full agentic workflow and the Market Data-free variant evaluated on the same cases with identical prompts, models, and metrics. To isolate the incremental contribution of this stage, we report paired per-case differences for each metrics, defined as $\Delta m = m_{\text{full}} - m_{\text{(w/oMarket Data)}}$. Positive Δm therefore indicates that the Market Data stage improves performance, with particular attention to evidence grounding and target-window focus.

Table 5. Per-zone performance deltas (agentic-no market data) with 95% bootstrap confidence intervals

Zone	N	Δ Reliability	Δ Calibration	Δ Unsupported exogenous assertions	Δ Exogenous mentions	Δ Target-neighbourhood
Bulgaria	22	+0.332 [+0.295, +0.368]	+0.000 [+0.000, +0.000]	+0.000 [+0.000, +0.000]	+0.000 [+0.000, +0.000]	+0.409 [+0.227, +0.591]
Czechia	27	+0.331 [+0.294, +0.369]	+0.000 [+0.000, +0.000]	+0.000 [+0.000, +0.000]	+0.000 [+0.000, +0.000]	+0.407 [+0.222, +0.593]
Hungary	24	+0.308 [+0.275, +0.350]	+0.000 [+0.000, +0.000]	+0.000 [+0.000, +0.000]	+0.000 [+0.000, +0.000]	+0.292 [+0.125, +0.500]
Poland	19	+0.334 [+0.292, +0.376]	+0.000 [+0.000, +0.000]	+0.000 [+0.000, +0.000]	+0.000 [+0.000, +0.000]	+0.421 [+0.211, +0.632]
Romania	29	+0.319 [+0.284, +0.353]	+0.000 [+0.000, +0.000]	+0.000 [+0.000, +0.000]	+0.000 [+0.000, +0.000]	+0.345 [+0.172, +0.517]
Slovakia	29	+0.312 [+0.278, +0.347]	+0.000 [+0.000, +0.000]	+0.000 [+0.000, +0.000]	+0.000 [+0.000, +0.000]	+0.310 [+0.138, +0.483]
All	150	+0.322 [+0.306, +0.338]	+0.000 [+0.000, +0.000]	+0.000 [+0.000, +0.000]	+0.000 [+0.000, +0.000]	+0.360 [+0.280, +0.440]

4.7 Human evaluation

Automatic metrics quantify structural properties (timestamp presence, calibration signals, unsupported-claim heuristics), but they do not fully capture whether the explanation is useful and credible for market analysts. Thus, we also report the results obtained following a human evaluation in Table 6.

Table 6. Human evaluation ratings

<i>Metric</i>	Agentic (mean, 95% CI)	Baseline (mean, 95% CI)	Δ Agentic – Baseline (95% CI)	Krippendorff’s α
Overall (1-5)	3.77 [3.63, 3.90]	3.02 [2.83, 3.21]	0.74 [0.52, 0.97]	0.66
Helpfulness (1-5)	3.93 [3.78, 4.09]	2.88 [2.72, 3.02]	1.06 [0.86, 1.26]	0.61
Correctness (1-5)	3.93 [3.84, 4.02]	2.99 [2.80, 3.17]	0.94 [0.76, 1.14]	0.67
Clarity (1-5)	3.70 [3.61, 3.78]	3.21 [2.98, 3.43]	0.49 [0.24, 0.74]	0.43
Pairwise preference (win rate)	65.5% [52.2%, 77.8%]	6.7% [2.2%, 13.3%]	58.8% [41.1%, 75.6%]	0.48

4.8 Validation and robustness across all metrics

Table 7 summarizes baseline and agentic performance across all studied metrics, reporting mean values and the paired mean effect with 95% bootstrap confidence intervals and paired Cohen’s d .

Table 7. Baseline and agentic framework performance

<i>Metric</i>	Baseline mean	Agentic mean	Mean Δ (95% CI)	Cohen’s d
Reliability score	+0.617	+0.781	+0.164 [+0.132, +0.195]	0.844
Price-only disclaimer presence (Calibration)	+0.440	+1.000	+0.560 [+0.480, +0.640]	1.124
Unsupported exogenous assertions	+2.387	+2.000	-0.387 [-0.687, -0.107]	-0.208
Exogenous mentions	+3.840	+17.620	+13.780 [+13.327, +14.213]	4.927
Target-neighbourhood focus	+1.000	+1.000	0.000 [0.000, 0.000]	0.000

The validated estimates support the primary findings, indicating that the agentic workflow improves the reliability score and calibration, while reducing unsupported exogenous driver assertions. In contrast, the target-neighbourhood metric remains unchanged due to a ceiling effect.

Appendix A outlines the structured prompting architecture that operationalizes the agentic workflow and explains why it produces more reliable and calibrated outputs than a monolithic LLM. The *Planner Agent* first decomposes each user query into explicit analytic steps, ensuring that the diagnostic task is framed in a structured and transparent manner rather than answered in a single narrative pass. The *Market-Data Agent* then restricts itself strictly to the provided numeric inputs, summarizing patterns without inventing values and preserving the original features table unchanged. This constraint enforces numerical grounding and prevents data hallucination. The *Mechanism Agent* introduces plausible market explanations, but only based on detected patterns and provided quantitative notes, explicitly separating hypotheses from facts. The *Verifier Agent* acts as a critic, systematically identifying unsupported causal claims, numeric inconsistencies and missing data, thereby injecting epistemic discipline into the workflow. Finally, the *Synthesizer Agent* assembles the response under strict rules: evidence lines must remain unchanged, exogenous drivers cannot be stated as facts without inputs and any causal interpretation must be labeled as low-confidence when only price data is available. These prompts reveal a deliberate separation of reasoning roles, planning, grounding, hypothesizing, auditing and synthesizing, designed to reduce hallucinated causality, enforce timestamp alignment and calibrate uncertainty in 15-minute SDAC price diagnostics.

5. Discussions

The results demonstrate that architectural design materially affects the reliability and practical usability of LLM-based diagnostics in 15-minute electricity markets. Across 150 structured cases covering six Central and Eastern European bidding zones, the agentic workflow consistently outperformed the monolithic LLM baseline in terms of reliability, calibration, and reduction of unsupported exogenous assertions. The average improvement in reliability (+0.164) and the substantial increase in explicit price-only disclaimers (+0.560) indicate that the agentic system produces explanations that are not only coherent, but appropriately cautious under limited observability. In practical terms, this reduces the risk of overconfident or misleading causal narratives, that is an essential requirement in high-stakes environments such as day-ahead electricity trading and post-event market analysis.

A particularly relevant finding is the shift from unsupported causal claims toward hypothesis-style reasoning. While the agentic workflow mentions exogenous concepts more frequently, it simultaneously reduces ungrounded assertions. This suggests that structured decomposition and verification do not suppress analytical richness; rather, they reframe it in a calibrated manner. For traders and analysts, this translates into explanations that are more aligned with professional reasoning: observed price dynamics are clearly described, but exogenous drivers are explicitly marked as uncertain when not supported by data. Such behavior is essential for risk management, compliance documentation and internal reporting processes, where defensibility and traceability matter.

The consistency of improvements across bidding zones strengthens the practical relevance of the findings. Although effect sizes vary, being strongest in Romania and Slovakia and more modest in Bulgaria and Czechia, the direction of improvement is stable. This cross-zone robustness suggests that the architectural approach generalizes across heterogeneous market conditions within the CEE region. In interconnected markets where cross-border effects can propagate rapidly, reliable diagnostic tools become particularly valuable for understanding localized spikes and ramps without over-attributing causality.

A complementary Market Data ablation isolates which architectural component most directly enables the observed gains in grounding and target-interval traceability. When the Market Data agent is removed, overall reliability drops substantially ($\Delta_{\text{reliability}} = +0.322$, 95% CI [0.306, 0.338] across 150 cases), alongside a pronounced reduction in target-interval anchoring ($\Delta_{\text{target-near}} = +0.360$, 95% CI [0.28, 0.44]). The effect is consistent across bidding zones, indicating that structured, timestamp-indexed extraction is a structural dependency for producing evidence explicitly tied to the 15-minute interval of interest. Notably, disclaimer and exogenous-assertion deltas remain near zero in this ablation, suggesting that uncertainty calibration is largely enforced by shared Critic/Synthesizer safeguards, whereas the Market Data agent primarily contributes the grounding layer needed for interval-specific reasoning.

Human evaluation further confirms the utility of the approach. The agentic workflow received substantially higher ratings in overall quality, helpfulness, correctness and clarity, with a 65.5% pairwise preference rate. This indicates that improvements observed in automatic reliability metrics translate into perceived analytical value for human users.

The findings imply that deploying LLMs in high-frequency electricity market analytics requires more than prompt engineering; it requires architectural safeguards that enforce grounding and uncertainty calibration. The proposed agentic workflow offers a practical blueprint for safer and more trustworthy AI-assisted diagnostics in SDAC markets.

6. Conclusions

This study evaluated the performance of an agentic workflow against a baseline LLM in terms of reliability of 15-minute SDAC day-ahead market diagnostics. To isolate the architectural contribution, we held the underlying model and case information constant.

The agentic workflow (from planning to structured extraction, quantitative checks, mechanism constraints, verification and synthesis) achieved a substantial improvement in our reliability score (mean $\Delta = +0.164$, CI [+0.132, +0.195]) across 150 price-only cases from six Central and Eastern Europe bidding zones. The improvements were consistent across all zones, ranging from +0.129 (Bulgaria) to +0.201 (Slovakia), suggesting that they generalize beyond a single market context. The superior performance was mainly driven by stronger calibration to price-only inputs ($\Delta = +0.560$) and fewer unsupported exogenous assertions ($\Delta = -0.387$). It is important to assess that the agentic system mentioned exogenous concepts more often overall but framed them as hypotheses or missing evidence rather than as confirmed drivers, aligning the narrative strength with the available data.

Our automated metrics were complemented by human evaluation. On a 1-5 scale, the agentic workflow achieved a higher score on quality (3.77 versus 3.02) and had the largest gains on helpfulness and correctness. Furthermore, the proposed architecture obtained a strong pairwise preference (65.5%). The Krippendorff's α scores ranged from 0.43 to 0.67 across metrics, supporting that the observed improvements are robust to annotator variability.

Practically, the findings support safer deployment of AI systems in market diagnostics, risk management, and post-trade analysis. Traders benefit from more cautious and timestamp-anchored explanations of quarter-hour price movements, system operators gain structured diagnostic support, and

compliance teams obtain outputs that are more defensible and transparent. More broadly, the study provides a reproducible benchmark and methodological blueprint for trustworthy AI in high-frequency, structured time-series environments, extending beyond electricity markets to other regulated financial and energy domains.

A limitation of our study is that cases were constructed from day-ahead prices alone; therefore, causal attribution to exogenous factors (outages, forecast errors, congestion, cross-border constraints) cannot be confirmed, and our evaluation necessarily emphasizes grounding and uncertainty handling rather than true causal correctness. In addition, the unsupported-claim detector and calibration signal are heuristic, and the benchmark is scoped to six zones, which may not capture broader SDAC diversity. Future work will incorporate additional public signals (e.g., ENTSO-E Transparency data on load, generation, outages, flows and capacity) to enable stronger causal tests.

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Appendix A. Agents prompts

A.1 Planner agent prompt

System message

You are the Planner Agent for EU day-ahead electricity market analysis at 15-minute resolution.

Decompose the user's question into short analytic tasks. Output STRICT JSON.

User message template

Case:

```
- zone: {case["zone"]}
- resolution: {case.get("resolution","15m")}
- question: {case["question"]}
```

Return JSON with keys: intent, target_window (optional), tasks (list of short steps).

A.2 Market data agent prompt

System message

You are the Market-Data Agent. Summarize patterns strictly based on the provided numeric table.

Do not invent values. Output STRICT JSON.

User message template

```
Summary stats: {summary_stats}
Detected patterns (heuristic): {detected_patterns}
```

Return JSON with keys:

```
- summary_stats (object)
- detected_patterns (list of strings)
- features_table (keep as-is; do not rewrite)
IMPORTANT: Put the original features_table back in output unchanged.
```

features_table:

```
{features_table[:120]} # truncated preview; you must still output full table from
input state
```

A.3 Mechanism agent prompt

System message

You are the Market-Mechanism Agent for EU day-ahead markets (SDAC, 15-min MTU).

Given numeric patterns and relevant public events, propose plausible mechanisms and sanity checks.

Do not cite documents; only reason from provided inputs. Output STRICT JSON.

User message template

```
Zone: {case["zone"]}
Question: {case["question"]}
```

```
Market data summary:
{state["market_data"]["summary_stats"]}
Detected patterns:
{state["market_data"]["detected_patterns"]}
```

```
Quant notes:
{state["quant"]["key_effects"]}
{state["quant"]["counterfactual_notes"]}
```

Return JSON with:

```
- plausibility_checks (list)
- potential_market_mechanisms (list)
- warnings (list)
```

A.4 Verifier agent prompt

System message

You are the Critic/Verifier Agent. Your job: identify unsupported causal claims, numeric issues, and what data would be needed to be more certain. Be strict. Output STRICT JSON.

User message template

```
Zone: {case["zone"]}
```

```
Question: {case["question"]}
```

Inputs available:

- Market data summary: {state["market_data"]["summary_stats"]}
- Detected patterns: {state["market_data"]["detected_patterns"]}
- Quant: {state["quant"]}
- Mechanism: {state["mechanism"]}

Return JSON with keys:

- unsupported_claims (list)
- numeric_inconsistencies (list)
- missing_data_requests (list)
- revised_guidance (list) # how to phrase conclusions safely

A.5 Synthesizer agent prompt

System message

Return ONLY JSON matching the schema.

Do NOT change evidence lines; copy them exactly.

Do NOT state exogenous causes (load/RES/outages/congestion/flows) as facts unless provided in inputs.

If only price series is provided, describe observed patterns and label any causes as hypotheses with low confidence.

User message template

```
Zone: {zone}
```

```
Question: {case.get("question", "")}
```

```
Target timestamp: {target_ts}
```

KEEP these evidence lines EXACTLY (do not edit):

```
{evidence}
```

Observed patterns (put into top_drivers; do NOT make them causal):

```
{top_drivers}
```

Uncertainty (keep calibrated; no contradictions like "timestamps missing"):

```
{uncertainty}
```

Draft final_summary (include explicit low-confidence hypotheses, not facts):

```
{final_summary}
```

Return JSON with keys:

- top_drivers: list[str]
- evidence: list[str] (must be exactly as provided above)
- event_links: list (empty unless case.public_events is used)
- uncertainty: list[str]
- final_summary: string